

Seismic intensity and typhoon categories: the need for quantitative clarity in Japanese disaster communication

Hiroyuki Chihara
College of Education, University of the Ryukyus
Nishihara, Okinawa 903-0213, Japan
hc@trevally.net

March 10, 2026

Abstract

We examine the Japanese seismic intensity scale and the typhoon categories issued by the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA). Most of the official information is presented in non-quantitative and experience-based expressions, which may hinder accurate understanding and international comparison. We argue that these expressions should be reformulated in quantitative terms. In particular, we revisit the mathematical definition of the JMA seismic scale as provided on its website, and we propose a more precise formulation, together with explanatory examples and comparisons with international standards. Keywords: Japan Meteorological Agency, seismic scale, typhoon category, Japanese language.

1 Introduction

Earthquakes are familiar disasters for residents of the Japanese archipelago and surrounding areas, while typhoons are familiar disasters for residents of the East China Sea, South China Sea, and surrounding areas. Disaster-related news coverage of earthquakes, typhoons, and other disasters in Japan revolves mainly around information from the Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA). When typhoons, heavy rain, heavy snow, or extremely high or low temperatures are predicted, JMA officials often hold special press conferences to provide detailed information and urge caution among the public. Recently, Japanese citizens have come to trust such works of the JMA, and many feel strongly that this indicates an impending crisis. The author is one of those Japanese citizens.

However, the author feels uncomfortable with the frequent use of emotional or purely descriptive language in JMA press conferences, as well as with the implicit national framing of disaster information. In fact, we often hear “a strong earthquake”, “a very strong typhoon”, “historically highest temperature”, etc. The information expressed by these phrases are limited. Moreover, for example, when a strong earthquake occurred near Taipei, we usually

heard that an earthquake of Japanese seismic scale 3 occurred on Ishigaki Island. If we want to know the overall earthquake information, we need to see, e.g., the USGS website by ourselves. The Japanese media rarely reports disasters in Asia, and even within Japan, disasters outside of major cities such as Tokyo and Osaka are becoming less and less likely to be reported every year.

On January 1, 2025, a magnitude 7.6 earthquake hit Noto region, Ishikawa Prefecture, Japan. This is the main earthquake of the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquakes [3, 14]. While Japanese media had very limited footage from the scene, Chinese television station CCTV13 sent multiple reporting teams to the site and continued to report on the earthquake situation in detail, including broadcasting a large amount of footage from the Noto region. The author also watched a Chinese earthquake expert's commentary on CGTN (China Global News Network), and the author heard a phrase "Japanese seismic scale" for the first time. The author knew that outside Japan, the seismic scales are usually expressed by "magnitude", which is a logarithmic scale. But the author was very surprised to notice that the Japanese seismic scale is specific to Japan.

So the author visited the JMA site to look at the pages of the definition of the Japanese seismic scales [4–6]. On one hand, the pages [4, 5] explains the Japanese seismic scale in experience-based expressions. Depending on how you look at it, the JMA may seem like they are assuming that Japanese residents are unable to understand the definition of seismic intensity. On the other hand, the other page [6] tries to give the precise definition of the Japanese seismic scale, but fails to present a sufficiently precise definition. Unfortunately, this suggests a gap in the level of mathematical explanation provided.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the Japanese seismic intensity scale and the typhoon categories issued by the JMA, and to propose a more precise formulation together with explanatory examples and comparisons to international standards. In other words, the present paper aims to establish a level of science communication that can be reasonably understood by readers with a background in upper secondary mathematics and elementary mechanics. The discussion proceeds through the analysis and comparison of primary sources published by official agencies such as the JMA and the USGS. In Section 2 we examine the Japanese seismic scale, and in Section 3 we investigate the Japanese typhoon categories. Finally, we briefly discuss what to do in Section 4.

2 Japanese seismic scale

In general, moment magnitude is widely used for describing the intensity of earthquakes all over the world. So we first see how the USGS (the United States Geological Survey) deals with the intensity of earthquakes. In the web page [15], the USGS first states that magnitude is the size of the earthquake and an earthquake has a single magnitude. This means that an earthquake has a theoretically unique magnitude. The USGS also states that moment magnitude is based on physical properties of the earthquake derived from an analysis of all the wave forms recorded from the shaking. The USGS states the definition of the moment

magnitude as follows:

$$\text{Moment}(\text{Mo}) := \text{Rigidity} \times \text{Area} \times \text{Slip} \quad (\text{N} \cdot \text{m} = \text{kg} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{s}^2),$$

$$\text{Moment Magnitude} (\text{Mw}) := \frac{2}{3} \times (\log_{10}(\text{Mo}) - 9.1).$$

Even a reader with basic training in physics can see that moment magnitude is like the sum of the amount of cross-sectional destruction caused by an earthquake, and that magnitude is its logarithm. In particular, if the difference of moment magnitudes of two earthquakes is two, the size of the bigger earthquake is one thousand times of that of the smaller one. Moreover, in the web page [16] the USGS explains the Modified Mercalli intensity scale, which was developed in 1931 by the American seismologists Harry Wood and Frank Neumann [18]. See Fig. 1. The USGS clearly states that it does not have a mathematical basis; instead it is an arbitrary ranking based on observed effects. Generally speaking, the USGS explanations

Intensity	Shaking	Description/Damage
I	Not felt	Not felt except by a very few under especially favorable conditions.
II	Weak	Felt only by a few persons at rest, especially on upper floors of buildings.
III	Weak	Felt quite noticeably by persons indoors, especially on upper floors of buildings. Many people do not recognize it as an earthquake. Standing motor cars may rock slightly. Vibrations similar to the passing of a truck. Duration estimated.
IV	Light	Felt indoors by many, outdoors by few during the day. At night, some awakened. Dishes, windows, doors disturbed; walls make cracking sound. Sensation like heavy truck striking building. Standing motor cars rocked noticeably.
V	Moderate	Felt by nearly everyone; many awakened. Some dishes, windows broken. Unstable objects overturned. Pendulum clocks may stop.
VI	Strong	Felt by all, many frightened. Some heavy furniture moved; a few instances of fallen plaster. Damage slight.
VII	Very strong	Damage negligible in buildings of good design and construction; slight to moderate in well-built ordinary structures; considerable damage in poorly built or badly designed structures; some chimneys broken.
VIII	Severe	Damage slight in specially designed structures; considerable damage in ordinary substantial buildings with partial collapse. Damage great in poorly built structures. Fall of chimneys, factory stacks, columns, monuments, walls. Heavy furniture overturned.
IX	Violent	Damage considerable in specially designed structures; well-designed frame structures thrown out of plumb. Damage great in substantial buildings, with partial collapse. Buildings shifted off foundations.
X	Extreme	Some well-built wooden structures destroyed; most masonry and frame structures destroyed with foundations. Rails bent.

Figure 1: The Modified Mercalli Intensity Scale of 1931 (USGS Public Domain [15]).

are very easy to understand and each one is explained in a fair amount of detail, so if one has a basic knowledge of mathematics and physics at the upper secondary level, one will probably feel like one understands quite a bit. In particular, the precise mathematical expressions help readers to understand the descriptions. In other words, one can understand the outlines of the USGS explanations without referring the other references.

Next we look into the Japanese seismic scale. The current Japanese seismic scale was introduced by the JMA in 1996, and we call it the JMA seismic scale below. We remark that the JMA does not clearly state that the JMA introduced its own seismic scale. In the Japanese website [7], the JMA explains as follows:

In the past, seismic intensity was estimated based on bodily sensations and the surrounding conditions, but since April 1996, it has been automatically observed

and reported using seismic intensity meters. The seismic intensity announced by the Japan Meteorological Agency is the intensity observed at seismic intensity observation points installed throughout the country by the Japan Meteorological Agency, local governments, and the National Research Institute for Earth Science and Disaster Resilience.

This means that the JMA seismic scale had been an arbitrary ranking based on observed effects such as the Modified Mercalli intensity scale before April, 1996. After that the JMA seismic scale has been derived from processing the data of the observations. Actually, however, the JMA shows the table of the seismic intensities which is similar to that of the Modified Mercalli intensity scale in Fig. 2. According to the Japanese web page [8], the JMA held

Human perception and reaction, indoor situation, outdoor situation			
Seismic intensity	Human perception and reaction	Indoor situation	Outdoor situation
0	Imperceptible to people, but recorded by seismometers.	-	-
1	Felt slightly by some people keeping quiet in buildings.	-	-
2	Felt by many people keeping quiet in buildings. Some people may be awoken.	Hanging objects such as lamps swing slightly.	-
3	Felt by most people in buildings. Felt by some people walking. Many people are awoken.	Dishes in cupboards may rattle.	Electric wires swing slightly.
4	Most people are startled. Felt by most people walking. Most people are awoken.	Hanging objects such as lamps swing significantly, and dishes in cupboards rattle. Unstable ornaments may fall.	Electric wires swing significantly. Those driving vehicles may notice the tremor.
5 Lower	Many people are frightened and feel the need to hold onto something stable.	Hanging objects such as lamps swing violently. Dishes in cupboards and items on bookshelves may fall. Many unstable ornaments fall. Unsecured furniture may move, and unstable furniture may topple over.	In some cases, windows may break and fall. People notice electricity poles moving. Roads may sustain damage.
5 Upper	Many people find it hard to move; walking is difficult without holding onto something stable.	Dishes in cupboards and items on bookshelves are more likely to fall. TVs may fall from their stands, and unsecured furniture may topple over.	Windows may break and fall, unreinforced concrete-block walls may collapse, poorly installed vending machines may topple over, automobiles may stop due to the difficulty of continued movement.
6 Lower	It is difficult to remain standing.	Many unsecured furniture moves and may topple over. Doors may become wedged shut.	Wall tiles and windows may sustain damage and fall.
6 Upper	It is impossible to remain standing or move without crawling. People may be thrown through the air.	Most unsecured furniture moves, and is more likely to topple over.	Wall tiles and windows are more likely to break and fall. Most unreinforced concrete-block walls collapse.
7		Most unsecured furniture moves and topples over, or may even be thrown through the air.	Wall tiles and windows are even more likely to break and fall. Reinforced concrete-block walls may collapse.

Figure 2: The Explanation of the JMA Seismic Scale (JMS [4]).

five times Seismic Intensity Review Committee about the improvement of this table from December 8, 2008 to March 23, 2009. The committee's members are primarily seismological experts and officials from disaster-related ministries. The information provided in the table of Fig. 2 and the web pages [4, 5, 7] is essentially same as that of the Modified Mercalli intensity scale, that is, the relationship between the digits and observed effects. In particular, the following information is not explained at all.

- The JMA seismic scale is uniquely determined for a pair of an earthquake and a location of seismograph.

- The rough physical meaning of the JMA seismic scale.

In other words, all one can understand somehow is just that the JMA seismic scale is an index that shows the strength of shaking at the observation point, and based on experience, shaking with a seismic intensity of 6 Lower or higher will cause significant damage.

We now look at the definition of the JMA seismic scale at the Japanese web page [6]. The Wikipedia page [17] and the paper [11] are basically English translation of [6]. The description in [11, 17] are slightly more accurate than that in [6], and not sufficiently precise. In what follows we make use of the Fourier transform of one-variable function of the time variable $t \in \mathbb{R}$, where \mathbb{R} denotes the set of all real numbers. See Appendix A or [13] for instance. The summary of the direct English translation of the definition of the JMA seismic scale written in the Japanese web page [6] is as follows.

- (i) Derive the Fourier transforms of three components (East-West, North-South, Up-Down) of the digital acceleration record.
- (ii) A filter $F(f) = F_F(f) \cdot F_L(f) \cdot F_H(f)$ is applied to correct for the effects of seismic wave periods, where
 - $F_F(f) = 1/\sqrt{f}$ is a filter showing the effect of cycles.
 - $F_L(f) = \sqrt{1 - \exp(-8f^3)}$ is a low-cut filter.
 - $F_H(f)$ is a high-cut filter defined by $\nu := f/10$,

$$F_H(f) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 + \alpha\nu^2 + \beta\nu^4 + \gamma\nu^6 + \delta\nu^8 + \varepsilon\nu^{10} + \zeta\nu^{12}}},$$

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= 0.694, & \beta &= 0.241, & \gamma &= 0.0557, \\ \delta &= 0.009664, & \varepsilon &= 0.00134 & \zeta &= 0.000155. \end{aligned}$$

- (iii) Convert the filtered frequency-domain signals back into time-domain signals by inverse Fourier transform.
- (iv) Sum the acceleration components into a single composite acceleration by vector summation.
- (v) When calculating the total time during which the absolute value of the vector waveform is greater than or equal to A , find the value A so that this is exactly 0.3 seconds.
- (vi) The instrumental intensity I is defined by $I := 2 \log_{10} A + 0.94$. The JMA seismic intensity scale is determined by the following table.

Table 1. The JMA seismic intensity

seismic intensity		seismic intensity	
0	$I < 0.5$	5 Lower	$4.5 \leq I < 5.0$
1	$0.5 \leq I < 1.5$	5 Upper	$5.0 \leq I < 5.5$
2	$1.5 \leq I < 2.5$	6 Lower	$5.5 \leq I < 6.0$
3	$2.5 \leq I < 3.5$	6 Upper	$6.0 \leq I < 6.6$
4	$3.5 \leq I < 4.5$	7	$6.5 \leq I$

There are two problems:

(P1) The JMA does not explain the following:

- What the observation is, the physical meaning of the observation, and the type of the mathematical form of the data.
- The purpose of the filtering process, and the roles of the parts of filters.
- The physical meaning of the representative value A and the instrumental intensity I .

(P2) The explanation of the filtering process is not precise mathematically at all.

In other words, one cannot understand what the observation is, the physical meaning of the observation and outputs, and the spirit of the design of the filters at all.

In what follows we reconstruct the definition of the JMA seismic scale so that anyone with a basic knowledge of mathematics and mechanics at the upper secondary level can roughly understand it. Let $t \in \mathbb{R}$ be the time variable. Basically the observation data must be a function on \mathbb{R} since its Fourier transform is considered. In the above the frequency f seems to be nonnegative, but it must take any real number. So we denote the frequency by $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$. Probably f means $|\tau|$. Then the symbols of filters are even functions. If we take the inverse Fourier transform, we need to deal with a function of $\tau \in \mathbb{R}$ unless the observation data is an even function. In general, dealing only with nonnegative frequencies is wrong if the inverse Fourier transform is used.

Observation data. Fix an arbitrary three-dimensional Cartesian coordinate system with the origin at the observation point. In the Japanese web page [6], the axes are East-West, North-South, and Up-Down. As we will mention below, the instrumental intensity I is invariant under the rotation of the axes. Real seismometer's data is a function of finite discrete time, that is. a finite sequence. Let $\delta > 0$ be a time step, and define a sequence of time by $t_n := n\delta$ ($n = 0, \pm 1, \pm 2, \dots$). Suppose that the earthquake begins at t_1 and ends at t_N with some positive integer $N > 1$. Consider the data of acceleration

$$\{\vec{a}(t_n) : n = 1, \dots, N\}, \quad \vec{a}(t_n) = (a_x(t_n), a_y(t_n), a_z(t_n)).$$

Set $\vec{a}(t_n) := \vec{0}$ for $n < 1$ or $n > N$. We define the data as a function on \mathbb{R} by

$$\vec{a}(t) := \frac{t_{n+1} - t}{\delta} \vec{a}(t_n) + \frac{t - t_n}{\delta} \vec{a}(t_{n+1}), \quad t_n = n\delta \leq t < (n+1)\delta = t_{n+1}.$$

Then $\vec{a}(t)$ is a continuous function on \mathbb{R} , and $\vec{a}(t) = \vec{0}$ for $t \leq 0 = t_0$ or $t \geq (N+1)\delta = t_{N+1}$. In particular, the three components of $\vec{a}(t)$ is integrable on \mathbb{R} .

Filter and its effects. Set $\sigma_F(\tau) := F_F(|\tau|)$, $\sigma_L(\tau) := F_L(|\tau|)$, $\sigma_H(\tau) := F_H(|\tau|)$, and $\sigma(\tau) := F(|\tau|) = \sigma_F(\tau)\sigma_L(\tau)\sigma_H(\tau)$. Then $\sigma_F(\tau)$, $\sigma_L(\tau)$, $\sigma_H(\tau)$, and $\sigma(\tau)$ are even functions. Let us briefly explain the role of the symbol $\sigma(\tau)$. Using Taylor's formulas $\sqrt{1+\varepsilon} = 1 + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon)$ and $e^\varepsilon = 1 + \varepsilon + \mathcal{O}(\varepsilon^2)$ for a small real number ε , we deduce that $0 \leq \sigma_L(\tau) \leq 1$,

$$\sigma_L(\tau) = 2\sqrt{2}|\tau|^{3/2}(1 + \mathcal{O}(\tau^3)) \quad \text{near } \tau = 0,$$

$$\sigma_L(\tau) = 1 + \mathcal{O}(\exp(-8|\tau|^3)) \quad \text{as } |\tau| \rightarrow \infty.$$

The behavior of the symbol of the high-cut filter $\sigma_H(\tau)$ is easy to see that $0 < \sigma_H(\tau) \leq 1$,

$$\sigma_H(\tau) = 1 + \mathcal{O}(\tau^2) \quad \text{near } \tau = 0,$$

$$\sigma_H(\tau) = \mathcal{O}(|\tau|^{-6}) \quad \text{as } |\tau| \rightarrow \infty.$$

Combining the above estimates, we obtain

$$\sigma(\tau) = 2\sqrt{2}|\tau|(1 + \mathcal{O}(\tau^2)) \quad \text{near } \tau = 0,$$

$$\sigma(\tau) = \mathcal{O}(|\tau|^{-13/2}) \quad \text{as } |\tau| \rightarrow \infty. \quad (1)$$

The role of $\sigma_F(\tau) = 1/\sqrt{|\tau|}$ is to stress the effect of the low frequency part, say $1 \leq |\tau| \leq 100$. It is known that human beings are sensitive to low frequency vibrations. See [2] for instance. The role of $\sigma_L(\tau)$ is to suppress dispersion of $\sigma_F(\tau)$ as $\tau \rightarrow 0$. Indeed we deduce that $\sigma_F(\tau)\sigma_L(\tau)$ is a bounded nonnegative function on \mathbb{R} and

$$\sigma_F(\tau)\sigma_L(\tau) = 2\sqrt{2}|\tau|(1 + \mathcal{O}(\tau^3)) \quad \text{near } \tau = 0.$$

The role of $\sigma_H(\tau)$ is to remove high frequency noise and make the observation smooth. We now define the filter kernel $k(t)$ by

$$k(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{it\tau} \sigma(\tau) d\tau$$

$k(t)$ is well-defined since $\sigma(\tau)$ is integrable on \mathbb{R} . Moreover, the property (1) implies that $k(t)$ is five times continuously differentiable, and $k(t)$ and its derivatives up to order five are all bounded on \mathbb{R} . This is mainly due to the behavior of $\sigma_H(\tau)$ as $|\tau| \rightarrow \infty$. $\sigma(\tau)$ is a real-valued even function, so is $k(t)$ and

$$k(t) = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_0^{\infty} \cos(t\tau) \sigma(\tau) d\tau.$$

Filtering and the instrumental intensity. For the extended observation data $\vec{a}(t)$, the filtered observation data is defined by

$$k*\vec{a}(t) : \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k(t-s)\vec{a}(s)ds = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k(s)\vec{a}(t-s)ds = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} k(t+s)\vec{a}(s)ds,$$

where the last one of the above follows from $k(-t) = k(t)$. Three components of $k*\vec{a}(t)$ are well-defined since $k(t)$ is a bounded continuous function, and three components of $\vec{a}(t)$ are continuous and vanishing outside a common finite interval $[0, (N+1)\delta]$. Moreover, $k*\vec{a}(t)$ is five times continuously differentiable, and $k*\vec{a}(t)$ and its derivatives up to order five are all bounded on \mathbb{R} .

Set $\|\vec{x}\| := \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2}$ for a three dimensional vector $\vec{x} = (x, y, z)$. $\|\vec{x}\|$ is said to be the size of a vector \vec{x} , the standard norm of \vec{x} , the norm of \vec{x} induced by the standard

inner product of \mathbb{R}^3 , ℓ^2 -norm of \vec{x} or etc. Consider $\|k*\vec{a}(t)\|$, which is the size of the filtered acceleration vector. $\|\vec{x}\|$ is invariant under the action of rotations. So $\|\vec{a}(t)\|$ and $\|k*\vec{a}(t)\|$ are independent of the choice of the Cartesian coordinate system at the observation point. We define the positive scalar value A and the instrument seismic intensity I by the procedures of (v) and (vi) respectively. A is a representative value of the size of the acceleration vector. In particular, we see the definition I as $I = \log_{10}(A^2) + 0.94$. What is the physical meaning of A^2 ?

Physical meaning of A . Let $\vec{a}(t)$ denote the acceleration vector. Consider the physical meaning of $a(t) := \|\vec{a}(t)\|$ in two simple examples.

Newton's second law of motion. Let m be mass of a point mass, and let $\vec{f}(t)$ be an external force vector acting on the mass point. Then the Newton's second law of motion is formulated as $m\vec{a}(t) = \vec{f}(t)$. We immediately get

$$a(t) = \frac{\|\vec{f}\|}{m}.$$

The right hand side of the above is the size of the force vector acting on a unit mass.

Uniform circular motion. Consider uniform circular motion of the speed v and the radius r . In this case $a(t)$ becomes a positive constant, and is denoted by a . Then we have

$$a = \frac{v^2}{r} = \kappa v^2,$$

where $\kappa = 1/r$ is the curvature of the circle. We fix v and move $\kappa = 1/r$. a is proportional to the curvature κ .

Hence $a(t)$ express the size of the forcing vector acting on a unit mass and the curvature of the orbit of the motion. So the representative value A of an earthquake is thought to describe these quantities under the influence of the earthquake. Unfortunately, we could not find the meaningful physical quantities corresponding to A or A^2 .

The definition of the JMA seismic scale has been clarified by the above. But the explanation of its physical meaning that contributes to intuitive understanding is still insufficient.

3 Japanese typhoon category

When a typhoon, hurricane or cyclone occurs nearby, everyone wants to know what course it will take, when and where it will pass, with what strength, and how it will affect them. The combined picture in Fig. 3 shows the information of the super typhoon RAGASA at 0:15 am JST on September 21, 2025 sourced by the JMA, the Windy¹, and the Tropical Storm Risk (TSR)². All three organization provide when and where it will pass. The Windy and

¹A global weather service, <https://www.windy.com/>.

²A global information service developed from the UK government-supported project, <https://www.tropicalstormrisk.com/>.

Figure 3: Super typhoon RAGASA at 0:15 JST on September 21, 2025, Screenshots of JMA, Windy and Tropical Storm Risk.

the TSR also show the strength for some locations with digits or colors, and the JMA does not. In particular, the displayed information of the windy is based on the data sourced by the JMA. This means that the JMA can provide the information about the intensity of typhoons as well as the other organizations. Why does the JMA not do this? In reality, the JMA's web page is interactive, and one can see the intensity information at the centers by tapping the centers. But the displayed information of the JMA is the English translation of Japanese version, and the typhoon information style in Japan is completely different from the global standard. The intensity expressed in color or simple numbers is easy to convey, but other information is difficult to convey. See Fig. 4. The standard Japanese typhoon information consists of estimated course, current location of center, current central atmospheric pressure, a red-colored circle enclosing current storm zone, a yellow-colored circle enclosing current strong wind zone, the 10-minute maximum sustained wind near the center, and etc. The 10-minute maximum sustained wind is more than 25m/s(48.6knot) in storm zone, and more than 15m/s(29.1knot) in strong wind zone.

Let us take a closer look at the differences between the global standard way of expressing typhoon strength and the way it is expressed in Japan. The Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Wind Scale is widely used in the world for expressing the intensity of cyclones, hurricanes and typhoons. See Fig. 5. This classification is based on the observation of one-minute maximum sustained winds. This is very simple and easy to understand. In particular, category 1 or higher classes are called typhoons. This represents a level that requires particular vigilance, and is likely consistent with our everyday sense of the situation.

The JMA has its own typhoon intensity scale. There are two serious issues in this scale.

- This scale is not quantitative but experience-based, e.g., “a strong typhoon”, which corresponds to a typhoon category 1.

Figure 4: The JMA's interactive typhoon page.

Tropical Cyclone Windspeed Scale*				
Strength	Category	1 Minute Maximum Sustained Winds		
		knots	mph	km/h
Tropical Depression	TD	<34	<39	<63
Tropical Storm	TS	34-63	39-73	63-118
Typhoon	Cat 1	64-82	74-95	119-153
Typhoon	Cat 2	83-95	96-110	154-177
Typhoon	Cat 3	96-112	111-129	178-208
Typhoon	Cat 4	113-136	130-156	209-251
Super Typhoon	Cat 5	>136	>156	>251

Figure 5: The Saffir-Simpson Hurricane Wind Scale (sourced by the TSR).

- The Japanese version is different from the English version, which is relatively similar to the global standard. For example, a tropical storm in the Saffir-Simpson hurricane wind scale corresponds to a tropical storm or a severe tropical storm in the English version of the JMA scale. These two categories in the English version is called a Japanese word TAIFU which is the direct translation of a typhoon in the Japanese scale.

We combine the Saffir-Simpson hurricane wind scale, the English and Japanese versions of the JMA typhoon intensity scale in a table in Fig. 6.

We show more detail about the English and Japanese versions of the JMA typhoon intensity scale. Let us see two web pages [9, 10] of the JMA explaining JMA's scale and intensity of tropical storms in English and Japanese respectively. See Fig. 7 and Fig. 8. First of all, a distinctive feature of the JMA is that it has an index for classifying the size of typhoons. Size may be an important index for meteorological experts, but it may not be considered important information for the general public who receive the information. The English version of this

The Saffir–Simpson hurricane wind scale (SSHWS)		knots	Japanese Intensity/Category	
1-minute maximum sustained winds			10-minute maximum sustained winds	
Intensity	Category		English Category	Japanese Category
Tropical Depression	TD	<34	Tropical Depression	Tropical Depression
		34-46	Tropical Storm	
Tropical Storm	TS	46-64	Severe Tropical Storm	Typhoon
Typhoon	1	64-83	Typhoon	Strong Typhoon
Typhoon	2	83-96		
Typhoon	3	96-113	Very Strong Typhoon	Very Strong Typhoon
Typhoon	4	113-136		
Super Typhoon	5	136<	Violent Typhoon	Violent Typhoon

Figure 6: The comparison of hurricane, typhoon scales.

index for classifying the size of typhoons is exactly same as the Japanese version.

Tropical Cyclone Information : Scale and intensity of the tropical cyclone

Scale	
–	30-kt wind radius < 500 km
Large	500 km ≤ 30-kt wind radius < 800 km
Very large	800 km ≤ 30-kt wind radius

Intensity/Category	
Tropical Depression	Maximum wind speed < 17m/s (34kt)
Tropical Storm	17m/s (34kt) ≤ Maximum wind speed < 25m/s (48kt)
Severe Tropical Storm	25m/s (48kt) ≤ Maximum wind speed < 33m/s (64kt)
Typhoon	33m/s (64kt) ≤ Maximum wind speed < 44m/s (85kt)
Very Strong Typhoon	44m/s (85kt) ≤ Maximum wind speed < 54m/s (105kt)
Violent Typhoon	54m/s (105kt) ≤ Maximum wind speed

Figure 7: JMA’s typhoon scale and intensity in English [9].

We see the JMA’s classification of the intensity of typhoons. We express the Japanese word corresponding to “typhoon” by “TAIFU”, which may be originated by the pronunciation of typhoon. We have the following.

- A tropical storm in the sense of the Saffir-Simpson scale is said to be a tropical storm or a severe tropical storm in English, and a TAIFU in Japanese.
- A category 1 typhoon in the sense of the Saffir-Simpson scale is said to be a typhoon in English, and a strong TAIFU in Japanese.
- A category 2 or 3 typhoon in the sense of the Saffir-Simpson scale is said to be a very strong typhoon in English, and a very strong TAIFU in Japanese.
- A category 4 or 5 typhoon in the sense of the Saffir-Simpson scale is said to be a violent typhoon in English, and a violent TAIFU in Japanese.

The most serious issue is that a tropical storm in the sense of the Saffir-Simpson scale is called a TAIFU in Japanese. This is common in the JMA’s press conference and Japanese weather news. So most Japanese people, in particular, Japanese people living in the Japanese archipelago seem to imagine a tropical storm when they hear a TAIFU, and to think that a

強さの階級分け

階級	最大風速
強い	33 m/s (64ノット) 以上～44 m/s (85ノット) 未満
非常に強い	44 m/s (85ノット) 以上～54 m/s (105ノット) 未満
猛烈な	54 m/s (105ノット) 以上

大きさの階級分け

階級	風速 15 m/s以上の半径
大型 (大きい)	500 km以上～800 km未満
超大型 (非常に大きい)	800 km以上

Figure 8: JMA's typhoon intensity and scale in Japanese [10].

TAIFU approaching to them is not a serious problem. More concretely, most Japanese people living in the Japanese archipelago are not likely vigilant when a category 1 or more typhoon is approaching to them. This is a serious problem in terms of disaster prevention and should be improved. There is supposed to be a Japanese phrase “NETTAI-BOUFUU” corresponding to a tropical storm. See the translation by the Google Translate in Fig 9. Actually, however, almost all the Japanese people do not know the phrase NETTAI-BOUFUU. The typhoon

Figure 9: Translation of English phrases of tropical storms into Japanese by Google.

information issued by the JMA is not necessarily appropriate from a view point of disaster communication. The JMA is a reliable agency having the detail information and accurate analysis, and is not making full use of its abilities.

4 Discussion and conclusions

The Japan Meteorological Agency (JMA) is internationally trusted as a provider of observational data, which are widely used by global applications and research institutes. Also the JMA is really trusted as disaster prevention information providers by people living in Japan. However, the agency's science communication remains problematic: definitions often

diverge from international standards, explanations are insufficient, and English translations are inconsistent.

Expressions and capability. The JMA is arguably one of the most trusted governmental organizations in Japan in terms of scientific data acquisition. However, limitations in its modes of expression and choice of public indices prevent the agency from fully leveraging its technical capabilities. The gap between the JMA's technical competence and its public-facing communication represents a missed opportunity rather than a lack of scientific capability. From a disaster prevention perspective, it would be useful to improve the way information is disclosed to include numerical expressions in line with international standards. If the Japan Meteorological Agency wanted to do it, it could make these improvements quickly.

Mathematical sciences. A shortage of human resources with strong backgrounds in the mathematical sciences might be a serious problem of the JMA, in contrast to agencies such as the USGS or the NOAA (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration), where applied mathematicians play a central role in hazard modeling and risk communication. This is not a problem unique to the JMA; many science and engineering organizations across Japan face similar issues. In Japan first year university students study calculus and linear algebra. The amount is insufficient, and students encounter only a small number of concrete examples. Indeed, very thin mathematics textbooks are common in Japan. Moreover, most universities in the developed countries provide courses entitled "Computational Thinking", and Japanese universities rarely do it. We actually checked the online syllabus of computational thinking at MIT, Columbia University, ETH, and National University of Singapore. So the gap of mathematical literacy between developed countries and Japan would be widening. The JMA may not be ready to improve this situation, but they should work on it as soon as possible.

We will be glad if this article could be useful for science communication of disaster prevention information in Japan.

Disclosure statement

The author declares no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Data Availability

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new datasets were created or analyzed during the current study.

References

- [1] C. Bodnar et al, *A foundation model for the earth system*. Nature, **641** (2025), pp.1180–1187.

- [2] J. C. Guignard, *Human sensitivity to vibration*, Journal of Sound and Vibration, **15** (1971), pp.11–16.
- [3] Headquarters for Earthquake Research Promotion, “Evaluation of the 2024 Noto Peninsula Earthquakes”, January 15,2024,
<https://www.jishin.go.jp/main/chousa/24jannoto2/index-e.htm>.
- [4] Japan Meteorological Agency, “Tables explaining the JMA Seismic Intensity Scale”,
<https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/en/Activities/inttable.html>.
- [5] Japan Meteorological Agency, “Earthquake information : Explanation of the seismic intensity”,
<https://www.data.jma.go.jp/multi/quake/quakeadvisory.html?lang=en>.
- [6] Japan Meteorological Agency, “Calculation method for instrumental seismic intensity” (in Japanese),
<https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/kishou/known/jishin/kyoshin/kaisetsu/calcsindo.html>.
- [7] Japan Meteorological Agency, “About seismic intensity” (in Japanese),
<https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/kishou/known/shindo/index.html>.
- [8] Japan Meteorological Agency, “Seismic Intensity Review Committee” (in Japanese),
<https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/kishou/shingikai/jishin/shindo-kentokai/index.html>.
- [9] Japan Meteorological Agency, “Tropical Cyclone Information: Scale and intensity of the tropical cyclone”
<https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/kishou/known/typhoon/1-3.html>.
- [10] Japan Meteorological Agency, “The size and strength of the typhoon” (in Japanese),
<https://www.jma.go.jp/jma/kishou/known/typhoon/1-3.html>.
- [11] K. R. Karim and F. Yamazaki, *Correlation of JMA instrumental seismic intensity with strong motion parameters*, Earthquake Engineering and Structural Dynamics, **31** (2002), pp.1191–1212.
- [12] Microsoft, “Aurora Forecasting: A flexible 3D foundation model of the atmosphere”,
<https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/project/aurora-forecasting/>.
- [13] E. M. Stein and R. Shakarchi, “Fourier Analysis: An Introduction”, Princeton University Press, Princeton, NJ, 2003.
- [14] United States Geological Survey, “M 7.5 - 2024 Noto Peninsula, Japan Earthquake”,
<https://earthquake.usgs.gov/earthquakes/eventpage/us6000m0x1/pager>.

- [15] United States Geological Survey, “Earthquake Magnitude, Energy Release, and Shaking Intensity”,
<https://www.usgs.gov/programs/earthquake-hazards/earthquake-magnitude-energy-release-and-shaking-intensity>.
- [16] United States Geological Survey, “The Modified Mercalli Intensity Scale”,
<https://www.usgs.gov/programs/earthquake-hazards/modified-mercalli-intensity-scale>.
- [17] Wikipedia, “Japan Meteorological Agency seismic intensity scale”
<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/JapanMeteorologicalAgencyseismicintensityscale>.
- [18] H. O. Wood and F. Neumann, *Modified Mercalli intensity scale of 1931*, Seismological Society of America Bulletin, **21(4)** (1931), pp.277–283.

A Fourier transform and Fourier multipliers

We briefly explain the Fourier transform and Fourier multipliers. See [13] for instance. But we employ a slightly different style. Denote by \mathbb{R} the set of all real numbers. Let $a(t)$ be an integrable function of $t \in \mathbb{R}$, that is,

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} |a(t)| dt < \infty.$$

We can define the Fourier transform $\mathcal{F}a$ of a by

$$\mathcal{F}a(\tau) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{-it\tau} a(t) dt, \quad \tau \in \mathbb{R}.$$

Set $\mathcal{F}^*a(\tau) := \mathcal{F}a(-\tau)$. If $\mathcal{F}(a)(\tau)$ happens to be an integrable function on \mathbb{R} , then we have the Fourier inversion formula:

$$a(t) = \mathcal{F}^* \mathcal{F}a(t) := \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i(t-s)\tau} a(s) ds \right) d\tau.$$

We split $a(t)$ into an even part and an odd part:

$$a(t) = \frac{a(t) + a(-t)}{2} + \frac{a(t) - a(-t)}{2}.$$

Then we have

$$\mathcal{F}a(\tau) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} \cos(t\tau) \frac{a(t) + a(-t)}{2} dt + i \sqrt{\frac{2}{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} \sin(t\tau) \frac{a(t) - a(-t)}{2} dt.$$

If $a(t)$ is a real-valued function, then its even part becomes the real part of $\mathcal{F}a(\tau)$, and its odd part becomes the imaginary part of $\mathcal{F}a(\tau)$.

We now introduce Fourier multipliers. Let $\lambda(\tau)$ be a continuous and integrable function on \mathbb{R} . The Fourier multiplier Λ associated with the symbol λ is defined by

$$\Lambda a(t) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{it\tau} \lambda(\tau) \mathcal{F}a(\tau) d\tau = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \left(\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{i(t-s)\tau} \lambda(\tau) a(s) ds \right) d\tau.$$

Change the order of the integrations of the right hand side of the above. We deduce that

$$\Lambda a(t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t-s)a(s)ds = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(s)a(t-s)ds,$$

$$h(t) := \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}}\mathcal{F}^*\lambda(t) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} e^{it\tau}\lambda(\tau)d\tau.$$

The definition of Λa is said to be the convolution of h and a denoted by $h*a$. Fourier multipliers are sometimes called filters also.

In what follows we consider an example of Fourier multipliers. Let $a(t)$ be a function defined by

- $a(1) = 3, a(2) = 1, a(3) = 2, a(4) = 1$, and $a(n) = 0$ for any integer n other than $1, 2, 3, 4$.
- The graph of $a(t)$ is defined by the line segment joining two points $(n, a(n))$ and $(n+1, a(n+1))$ for any integer n . More precisely, for any integer n , define

$$a(t) := (n+1-t)a(n) + (t-n)a(n+1) \quad n \leq t < n+1.$$

Then the graph of $a(t)$ is a line graph and $a(t) = 0$ for $t \leq 0$ or $t \geq 5$. Set $h(t)$ by

$$h(t) := \frac{3003}{2048}(1-t^2)^6 \quad (|t| < 1), \quad h(t) := 0 \quad (|t| \geq 1).$$

Then $h(-t) = h(t)$, $h(t) \in C^5(\mathbb{R})$, that is, $h(t)$ is five times continuously differentiable on \mathbb{R} , and $h(t)$ is normalized as follows

$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(t)dt = \int_{-1}^1 h(t)dt = 1.$$

Moreover, we have

$$\Lambda a(t) = h*a(t) = \int_{-1}^1 h(s)a(t+s)ds.$$

We show the graphs of $h(a)$, $a(t)$ and $\Lambda a(t)$ drawn by the computer algebra system Mathematica in Fig. 10. Every corner formed by the two line segments becomes smooth by the effect of the filter.

Figure 10: The filter $h(t) = 3003(1 - t^2)^6/208$, and original data and filtered data